

Syntheses of Furano Compounds. Part XLV Syntheses of 1-Oxo-1H-Benzo[b]Furo[4,3-d]Indeno [2',1':5,6]Pyrans and Nitrogen Analogues

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It is shown that cyclisations of α -benzyl-2-carboxybenzo[b]furan-3-acetic acids lead to formation of the corresponding 1-oxo-1H-benzo[b]furo[4,3-d]indeno[2',1':5,6]pyrans. Some reactions of these pyrones have been studied.

METHYL 2-methoxycarbonylbenzo[b]furan-3-acetate¹(I) underwent Stobbe condensation² with aromatic aldehydes in alcoholic sodium methoxide leading to benzylidenedicarboxylic acids (II-V). These acids were characterised by corresponding anhydrides which were readily obtained on treatment with acetic anhydride. On reduction, the Stobbe products afforded the dihydro derivatives (VI-IX).

I

- (II) $R=R_1=H, R_2=CH_3$
(III) $R_1=R_2=H, R=OCH_3$
(IV) $R=R_2=H, R_1=OCH_3$
(V) $R=R_1=R_2=H$

- (VI) $R=R_1=H, R_2=CH_3$
(VII) $R_1=R_2=H, R=OCH_3$
(VIII) $R=R_2=H, R_1=OCH_3$
(IX) $R=R_1=R_2=H$

- (X) $R=OCH_3$
(XI) $R=H$

The compound (IX) on treatment with polyphosphoric acid underwent cyclodehydration and lactonisation giving the indenopyrone³ (X and XI) ($\nu_{C=O}$ 1725 cm^{-1}) which showed a brilliant violet fluorescence in sulphuric acid due to the formation of 1-hydroxyisobenzo[b]furopyrylium salt (XIII). The cyclodehydration of (VIII) led to the formation of a single product which was assigned the structure (X)⁴.

The pyrones (X and XI) on treatment with alcoholic ammonia⁵ afforded the related α -pyridones (XIV and XV). On treating (XV) with phosphorus oxychloride and phosphorus pentachloride⁶, the chloro compound (XVI) was obtained (phosphorus oxychloride alone was ineffective) which was catalytically dechlorinated to (XVII).

(XII) $R = OCH_3$
 (XIII) $R = H$

(XIV) $R_1 = OH, R = OCH_3$
 (XV) $R_1 = OH, R = H$
 (XVI) $R_1 = Cl, R = H$
 (XVII) $R = R_1 = H$

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. The IR spectra were determined in KBr pellet in Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer Model 237.

α -*p*-Methylbenzylidene-2-carboxybenzo[*b*]furan-3-acetic Acid(II) :

A mixture of *p*-tolualdehyde (0.12 g) and methyl 2-methoxycarbonylbenzo[*b*]furan-3-acetate(I) (0.25 g) was added to a solution of sodium (0.03 g) in dry methanol (2 ml) and the mixture refluxed for 6 hrs. Solvent was then removed under reduced pressure to afford a colourless solid which was washed with ether, boiled with NaOH (1.5 ml; 10%) for 1.5 hrs and then acidified (conc. HCl) to furnish (II) which crystallised from aqueous acetic acid in colourless needles, m.p. 270° (decomp). (Found : C, 70.76 ; H, 4.29. $C_{19}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 70.80 ; H, 4.38%). The related anhydride was obtained by heating(II) with acetic anhydride, crystallised from acetic anhydride in glittering yellow needles, m.p. 209°. (Found : C, 74.96 ; H, 3.86. $C_{19}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 74.99 ; H, 3.97%) ; ν_{max} 1750 and 1780 cm^{-1} .

Reduction of (II) with Sodium Amalgam :

The compound(II) (0.55 g) was dissolved in 10% NaOH solution and reduced with sodium amalgam

(22.0 g ; 2%) for 48 hrs. The aqueous layer was filtered and acidified (conc. HCl) and extracted with ether. The ether solution was washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of ether afforded the benzyl compound(VI) as a thick viscous oil (0.5 g). (Found : C, 70.28 ; H, 4.89. $C_{19}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 70.36 ; H, 4.98%).

α -*o*-Methoxybenzylidene-2-carboxybenzo[*b*]furan-3-acetic Acid(III) :

Compound(I) and *o*-methoxybenzaldehyde similarly gave(III) in colourless small needles from aqueous acetic acid, m.p. 224° (decomp). (Found : C, 67.41 ; H, 4.08. $C_{19}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 67.45 ; H, 4.17%) ; ν_{max} 1675 and 1700 cm^{-1} . The related anhydride was obtained in yellow needles from acetic anhydride, m.p. 224°. (Found : C, 71.10 ; H, 3.61. $C_{19}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 71.25 ; H, 3.78%).

The dihydro derivative(VII) was similarly obtained on reduction as a colourless viscous oil. (Found : C, 66.91 ; H, 4.71. $C_{19}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 67.05 ; H, 4.75%).

α -*m*-Methoxybenzylidene-2-carboxybenzo[*b*]furan-3-acetic Acid(IV) :

This was obtained from (I) and *m*-methoxybenzaldehyde as before in colourless shining plates from aqueous acetic acid, m.p. 228° (decomp). (Found : C, 67.45 ; H, 4.21. $C_{19}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 67.45 ; H, 4.17%) ; ν_{max} 1685 and 1710 cm^{-1} .

The corresponding anhydride was obtained in yellow plates from acetic anhydride, m.p. 197°. (Found : C, 71.18 ; H, 3.62. $C_{19}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 71.25 ; H, 3.78%).

The dihydro derivative(VIII) was obtained as a colourless viscous oil. (Found : C, 66.96 ; H, 4.72. $C_{19}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 67.05 ; H, 4.75%).

1-Oxo-1*H*-5'-methoxybenzo[*b*]furo[4,3-*d*]indeno[2',1' : 5,6]pyran :

The benzyl compound (VIII, 0.55 g) was heated with polyphosphoric acid (25.1 g) at 120-30° for 5 hrs. The resulting mass was poured over crushed ice and stirred when a black product separated. This was extracted with benzene ; the benzene layer washed successively with aqueous $NaHCO_3$, water and dried ($MgSO_4$). Removal of benzene gave a yellow solid which crystallised from acetic acid in yellowish brown needles (0.23 g), m.p. 233°. (Found : C, 74.82 ; H, 3.87. $C_{19}H_{12}O_4$ requires C, 74.99 ; H, 3.97%) ; ν_{max} 1741 cm^{-1} .

The compound dissolved in conc. H_2SO_4 giving yellow colour and imparting brilliant green fluorescence.

1-Oxo-1H, 2H-5'-methoxybenzo [b] furo [4,3-d] indeno [2',1' : 5,6]-pyridine(XIV) :

The foregoing compound (0.1 g) was taken in a sealed tube with alcoholic ammonia (5 ml; saturated at 0°) and heated at 140° for 5 hrs. It was then cooled to furnish brown crystals of (XIV) in quantitative yield which crystallised from acetic acid in light yellowish brown crystalline solid, m.p. >300°. (Found : N, 4.56. $C_{18}H_{18}O_8N$ requires N, 4.62%); ν_{max} 1665 cm^{-1} .

α -Benzylidene-2-carboxybenzo [b] furan-3-acetic Acid(V) :

Compound(I) on Stobbe condensation with benzaldehyde similarly gave (V) in colourless shining granules from aqueous acetic acid, m.p. 248° (decomp). (Found : C, 70.11; H, 3.67. $C_{18}H_{12}O_5$ requires C, 70.13; H, 3.92%); ν_{max} 1698 and 1720 cm^{-1} .

The related anhydride was obtained as orange shining needles from acetic anhydride, m.p. 207°. (Found : C, 74.41; H, 3.35. $C_{18}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 74.48; H, 3.47%).

The benzyl compound(IX) was obtained on reduction as colourless thick oil. This was treated with polyphosphoric acid without purification.

1-Oxo-1H-benzo[b] furo [4,3-d] indeno [2',1' : 5,6] pyran (XI) :

The foregoing oil (0.2 g) was heated with polyphosphoric acid (10.0 g) at 120-30° for 12 hrs. On working up, (XI) was obtained which crystallised from benzene in yellow needles, m.p. 267°. (Found : C, 78.76; H, 3.60. $C_{18}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 78.82; H, 3.68%); ν_{max} 1725 cm^{-1} . The compound showed a brilliant violet fluorescence in conc. H_2SO_4 .

1-Oxo-1H, 2H-benzo [b] furo [4,3-d] indeno [2',1' : 5,6] pyridine(XV) :

The pyrone (XI, 0.1 g) was heated at 140° with ethanolic ammonia (5 ml, saturated at 0°) in a sealed tube for 5 hrs. On working up, yellowish brown crystals of the pyridine(XV) were obtained from acetic acid, m.p. >370°. (Found : C, 79.06;

H, 3.90; N, 5.04. $C_{18}H_{11}O_2N$ requires C, 79.11; H, 4.06; N, 5.13%); ν_{max} 1660 cm^{-1} .

1-Chlorobenzo[b] furo [4,3-d] indeno [2',1' : 5,6] pyridine(XVI) :

A mixture of foregoing compound (0.05 g), $POCl_3$ (1.5 g) and PCl_5 (1.5 g) was heated at 165-70 for 6 hrs. The resulting mixture was cooled, poured over crushed ice, basified with ammonia and extracted with chloroform. The dried chloroform solution was filtered through an alumina column and the filtrate concentrated to afford colourless crystals. It crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in prisms, m.p. 216-17°. (Found : C, 73.81; H, 3.30. $C_{18}H_{10}ONCl$ requires C, 74.09; H, 3.43%).

Benzo [b] furo [4,3-d] indeno [2',1' : 5,6] pyridine (XVII) :

The foregoing chloro compound (0.05 g) in methanol was hydrogenated at room temperature in presence of KOH (0.03 g) using palladised charcoal (0.05 g; 10%). Absorption of hydrogen was complete in a few minutes. The mixture was filtered, the filtrate concentrated and diluted with water and extracted with ether; the ether solution washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the solvent afforded a yellow oil. The compound gave a dull yellow picrate which crystallised from alcohol in light yellow crystals, m.p. 189-90°. (Found : C, 59.39; H, 2.79; N, 11.51. $C_{18}H_{11}ON.C_6H_5O_7N_3$ requires C, 59.46; H, 2.88; N, 11.52%).

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